

GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

NATIONAL FIELDWORK REPORT DENMARK

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1. INTRODUCTION

According to Danish law, every citizen has equal constitutional rights and is entitled to equal protection and respect as regards human rights. GBV is perceived as a working environment issue and is addressed by the Working Environment Act. Furthermore, the principle of equality is incorporated in the Gender Equality Act, which promotes equality between women and men, prevents direct or indirect discrimination on the grounds of gender, and counteracts harassment and sexual harassment.

Denmark does not have any explicit national policies to prevent and combat GBV in universities and research organisations. No specific financial or human resources have hence been allocated at the national level for action plans against GBV in this sector. Moreover, there is a lack of studies focusing in particular on GBV as to prevalence, prevention, prosecution or effects of harassment in universities and research organisations. While there is legislation (anti-discrimination legislation, working environment legislation, gender equality legislation, education environment legislation as well criminal legislation) that addresses harassment, sexual harassment and bullying as well as the physical and psychological environment, there is no specific GBV legislation targeting universities and research organisations in particular.

Thus, various policy initiatives and, over time, legislation are based on the approach to GBV as a working environment and a gender discrimination problem. Accordingly, GBV, and sexual harassment, in particular, has been addressed as a gender equality issue, at the same time as it has been perceived as a working environment issue and handled as such in accordance with the Danish tradition of including the social partners in regulating labour relations.

If no, please give us your expert opinion on why you think no policy concerning GBV in universities and research organisations has been adopted by national/regional authorities in your country or indicate whether GBV in universities and research organisations are handled in some other way?

Since GBV is perceived as gender equality and working environment issue, no specific education or research authority at the national level is in charge of formulating policies and combating GBV at universities and research organisations. According to the gender equality and working environment legislation and regulations, universities and research organisations, as all working environments in Denmark, are expected to address the issue themselves, preventing and combating GBV in the environment. Some issues related to gender discrimination and the psychological environment have been included in the APV, i.e. the Workplace Assessment of working environments, which is required by law to be carried out by all working environments in Denmark and must be revised at least every three years. The Danish Working Environment Authority (WEA) outlines the legal requirements that organisations or companies APVs must

fulfil. There are thus general guidelines on how to make use of the APV and what to include in the assessment, but the specific content of the APV is tailor-made to each organisation and hence formulated by the organisations and companies themselves.

For a long time, the issue of GBV in Danish universities and research organisations has not been addressed. Consequently, the actual prevalence of GBV in universities and research organisations in Denmark is not known. Knowledge on prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services and partnerships at the national level is also limited. The focus has traditionally been on sexual harassment in the labour market, and it is therefore primarily in this area that knowledge about the prevalence of harassment has been collected.

However, the emergence of the #MeToo movement has put more attention to sexual harassment in all parts of society, including the universities, although the movement and its effects have been somehow delayed, compared to other countries. Experiences of sexual harassment among university students were focused on in the public debate, in particular in February 2018, when 48 students from five Danish universities sent an open letter to the rectors of their universities, which was published in the newspaper Information. The letter was critical of how the universities dealt with cases of sexual harassment and asked for more active engagement in terms of policies for prevention as well as prosecution (Guschke et al., 2019).

The debate resulted in the survey "Undersøgelse af uønsket seksuel adfærd rettet mod studerende på de danske universiteter", focusing on sexual harassment among students at Danish universities. The survey was conducted in 2018 by Universities Denmark (Danske Universiteter) and the National Union of Students in Denmark (Danske Studerendes Fællesråd). The questionnaire was sent to all Danish students. 1.194 students reported that they had been exposed to unwanted sexual experiences. The questionnaire has distinguished between the following types of unwanted sexual behaviour: Offensive verbal comments of a sexual nature, unwanted sharing of material with sexual content online, unwanted physical touch, and unwanted experience where someone has exposed himself.

On the basis of this study, Universities in Denmark and the National Union of Students in Denmark, as well as each individual university, carried out initiatives to address the key problems that the study pointed to. In particular, three initiatives were highlighted. All universities set to work towards establishing support bodies for students to turn to in case they experience unwanted sexual behaviour, harassment or abuse, based on the following principles: (i) the support must be available in a safe space and within a confidential framework, and there must be clearer procedures for handling the case; (ii) the universities are also working to ensure that questions about unwanted sexual behaviour are embedded in the studies of the study environment that the universities regularly carry out. The studies shall ensure knowledge update and a continuous focus on the area both locally and centrally; (iii) Universities Denmark and the National Union of Students in Denmark will continue a systematic dialogue in the area with a view to increasing exchange of experience about opportunities, initiatives and problems with unwanted sexual behaviour targeted students.

A recent initiative, not specifically targeted GBV, has been carried out in connection with "Uddannelseszoom" (Education Zoom), a questionnaire survey carried out by the Ministry of Higher Education and Science. Every two years, all the Danish students participate in the survey Education Zoom. The questionnaire is sent to students in higher education to collect their experiences on different issues, from learning and teaching to the study environment and well-being. Education Zoom is primarily a tool that supports the students in connection with their choice of education and study programmes. It provides comprehensive data on the quality of

different study programmes and their relevance in relation to the job market. In the 2020 questionnaire, new questions were added, namely whether the students had experienced sexism and unwanted sexual attention and how the covid-19 lockdown has affected them. The questionnaire included three new questions on sexism and sexual harassment and four questions on covid-19 related issues. All students were asked whether they had experienced unwanted sexual attention in their study environment, such as comments or unwanted physical contact, by whom and where. The questions were formulated with input from experts in KVINFO (an institute under the Ministry of Culture) and the Ministry of Gender Equality. The outcome of the survey has not yet been made available.

In addition, very recently (autumn 2020), a delayed #MeToo movement, mobilising women researchers from all Danish universities, put the issue on the public agenda and hence the agenda of universities and research organisations for the first time. This led to an ongoing process of identifying the problems at the institutional level and introducing initiatives to address, in particular sexual harassment.

Another initiative addressing, in particular, sexual harassment comprises a survey conducted by *Magisterbladet* (the publication of the Danish Association of Masters and PhDs) initiated in 2018. The survey was carried out among 1,017 university students, including 811 women, organized members of the Danish Association of Masters and PhDs. The survey focused primarily on the student's experiences as to gender-based and sexual harassment during their studies (*Magisterbladet* 2018).

2. MAPPING OF POLICIES AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

The Danish legislation and the various policy initiatives are based on the approach to harassment and sexual harassment as gender discrimination and as a gender equality issue as well as a working environment issue. The harassment and sexual harassment policy in Denmark is therefore based on a political, union and legal track with a focus on the obstacles to dealing with sexual harassment in the workplace. The handling of harassment and sexual harassment has hence been developed in an area that spans legislation, political and union regulations and law practising with a focus on arenas and actors (Borchorst & Agustin 2017).

The legislation that addresses harassment as a human rights and gender discrimination issue, and working environment and educational environment issue are the following:

Danmarks Riges Grundlov. Lov nr. 169 af 05/06 1953 [Grundloven], The Constitution: refers to the human rights. <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/1953/169>

Lov om arbejdsmiljø, Lovbekendtgørelse nr. 1072 af 07/09/2010 [Arbejdsmiljøloven] The Working Environment Act: refers to the working environment and the general regulations for a secure and healthy working environment. <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2005/268>

Lov om elevers og studerendes undervisningsmiljø, Lov nr. 166 af 14/03/2001 [Undervisningsloven] The Educational Environment Act: refers to the physical, psychological and aesthetics of the educational environment. However, the law does not contain the same clarity as, for example, the Working Environment Act, as it is written in broader terms. This lack of precision may be due to the fact that it covers everything from small children in elementary school to students in upper secondary education and students in higher education. With a change in spring 2017, particular reference is made to mandatory work with the psychological environment and bullying in the education and teaching environment for primary and secondary

schools. Higher education and sexual harassment issues are not mentioned.
<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2017/316>

Lov om ligestilling af kvinder og mænd.Lovbekendtgørelse nr.1678 af 19/12 2013 [Ligestillingsloven] The Gender Equality Act: it was passed in Parliament in 2000 and has been amended over time. The aim of the Act is to promote equality between women and men, including equal integration, equal influence and equal opportunities in all functions of society, based on the principle of the equal worth of women and men. The law prevents direct and indirect discrimination based on gender and counteracts harassment and sexual harassment. The Act obliges employers to treat men and women equally at employment and dismissal and in relation to all other terms of employment. The obligation to equal treatment also applies to anybody that carries out supervision and educational activity. The Gender Equality Act prohibits hence any type of discrimination and defines harassment and sexual harassment as discrimination. § 1, sect. 5 defines harassment as "any form of unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical behaviour in relation to a person's gender", while § 1, sect. 6 states, "Sexual harassment exists when any unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical behaviour is exhibited with sexual undertones" - and in both cases "with the purpose or effect of violating a person's dignity, in particular by creating a threatening, hostile, degrading humiliating or unpleasant climate."
<https://danskelove.dk/ligestillingsloven>.

The Gender Equality Act ensures equal treatment in connection with public administration services and access to and supply of goods and services in the business sector. The law also obliges public authorities to implement gender mainstreaming to work for gender equality and incorporate gender equality in all planning and administration. The law also provides possibilities for positive special treatment. The Act has been enforced in particular by the Equal Treatment Board, which has made decisions in a large number of cases, in particular as regards the legitimacy of positive special treatment and affirmative actions. Once a year, the Minister for Gender Equality prepares a report and an action plan for gender equality for the Folketing (Parliament). Public authorities, companies and organizations are obliged (upon request) to provide the Minister for Gender Equality with the information on gender equality that is needed to prepare the annual report and action plan to be presented to the Parliament.

The Equal Treatment Act and the Equal Pay Act (No. 899 of 2008) are laws targeting equal treatment of women and men in the labour market. The laws are largely the result of the implementation of EU rules and contain uniform legal definitions of discrimination and sanctions. Danish legislation on discrimination and gender equality is to a large extent adapted to EU rules in this area, and especially in the area of labour law, EU rules play a crucial role. The international obligations are largely implemented in the legislation, but in the labour market, collective agreements are of increasing importance. In addition, there are some areas in the regulations, which are an expression of purely Danish rules, which apply to the Gender Equality Act (Borchorst and Agustin 2017).

In Denmark, working conditions are typically determined through individual contracts or collective agreements signed between the different partners in the labour market. Thus, the collective agreements that regulate salaries and working conditions are of great importance for how the principles of equal treatment and equal status in working life are implemented. In working life, the protection against gender-based and sexual harassment depends hence on the context in which harassment takes place. In purely private matters, the protection exists only in terms of enforcement of the criminal law, while there is extended protection in the context of the labour market. The protection in the education area is more diffuse, as the Education

Environment Act does not specifically address, for instance, sexual harassment, but only bullying, digital bullying and psychological harassment (Borchorst and Agustin 2017).

Denmark signed the Istanbul Convention in 2013 and ratified it on the 23 of April 2014. In Denmark, the national coordinating body, as defined by the Istanbul Convention, is an inter-ministerial working group, which targeted governmental measures in the area of violence against women even before the ratification of the Istanbul Convention. The working group is coordinated by the Department of Gender Equality (Ligestillingsafdelingen) in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (Udenrigsministeriet). Denmark had thereby introduced policies to combat violence against women long before the Istanbul Convention was signed. Despite the fact that Denmark supported the creation of networks and civil society organisations, the Danish state had not introduced its own concerted actions until the 2000s, when the inter-ministerial working group was established. However, civil society organisations (such as Danner) have been working to provide protection and support structures for women affected by violence since the 1980s (Lange, Molter and Wittenius 2020). Since 2002, Denmark has used action plans to implement strategies and measures in addressing violence against women and violence in close relationships (domestic violence). The most recent action plans deal with sexual violence and rape (2016), stalking (2016), honour-related conflicts (2017–2020) and domestic violence (2014–2017 and 2019–2022) (Ministry of Justice 2017: 2ff). A national agency named “Life Without Violence” (Ret Til Et Liv Uden Vold), was established in 2017 to consolidate knowledge and concrete measures in the area of domestic violence (GREVIO 2017, Institut for Menneskerettigheder 2014, Lev Uden Vold 2019).

In Denmark, the responsibility for the handling of harassment and sexual harassment is divided among different actors. The Ministry of Gender Equality coordinates the action plans and ensures that the plans are implemented centrally and locally. The Ministry of Health is responsible for the guidelines for health professional treatment, while the Ministry of Education is responsible for informing children and young people in the education system. The Ministry of Justice is responsible for criminal law and law enforcement with the police, the prosecution authorities and the courts as its areas of jurisdiction. The regions have the direct responsibility for professional health treatment in emergency rooms, hospitals and with general practitioners. The municipalities are responsible for offering temporary accommodation to abused women and their children in women's shelters and providing family counselling to women as well as psychological treatment to children in shelters. The police are responsible for direct contact with the victims and the perpetrators when violent behaviour is reported. The different authorities prepare internally or in collaboration with local actors joint safekeeping plans, which aim to ensure that victims of violence are protected (Institut for Menneskerettigheder 2014, Lange, Molter and Wittenius 2020).

In this context, it is important to mention the Danish Institute for Human Rights (Institut for Menneskerettigheder), which is an independent state-funded institution responsible for monitoring and reporting on the human rights situation in Denmark and advising the Government, Parliament, ministries and other public authorities. The mandate of the institute is to promote and protect human rights and equality in Denmark and abroad. As a national equality body, the institute is committed to promoting equal treatment addressing discrimination on the grounds of gender, racial or ethnic origin, age, religion and faith, including by conducting independent investigations into discrimination and by publishing reports and making recommendations on discrimination issues. The institute performs analysis of and research in the field of human rights and provides assistance to victims of discrimination. Moreover, the institute monitors the Danish state's efforts against violence in close relationships and reports

to the Government, the Parliament, and the UN and the Council of Europe's human rights bodies (Institut for Menneskerettigheder 2014).

3. DEBATES REGARDING #METOO AND THE ISTANBUL CONVENTION

Prior to Denmark's ratification of the Istanbul Convention, the Ministry of Justice carried out an analysis of the legislative consequences of such ratification. The Danish legal framework was found, with few exceptions, to fully comply with the content of the Convention. The Convention did, therefore, not entail significant changes in the Danish legal frame (Worch Jensen and Larsen 2016). Thus, the ratification of the Convention has not attracted particular attention in the public debate.

In 2017, the Council of Europe's expert group, Group of Experts on Action against Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (GREVIO) reviewed how Denmark complies with the Istanbul Convention. GREVIO's report (2017) was published in autumn 2017 with a number of critical points. Among others, the expert group criticized the fact that Denmark uses gender-neutral terms about violence, even though research shows that perpetrators of violence are predominantly men, while victims of violence are most often women (Deen et al. 2018, The Women's Council in Denmark 2017). In addition, GREVIO called on the Danish authorities to devote more resources to prevention, protection and care services to victims of violence against women. GREVIO also criticized Denmark for lacking gender-disaggregated data on violence.

With the emergence of the #MeToo movement, where millions of women shared their experiences of sexual abuse and sexual harassment, harassment was put on the public agenda in many countries, among others Denmark (although not to the same degree) and initiated a review of the protection rules against sexual harassment in the labour market.

As to the higher education and research sector, as mentioned earlier, inspired by the #MeToo movement, an initiative by students from five Danish universities in 2018 to send an open letter about experiences of sexual harassment to the rectors of their universities has led to a debate in the media about the issue. The open letter was a follow up of an initiative by students at Denmark's Technical University to put posters in the university corridors with testimonies from students about sexual abuse and sexist behaviour from staff, fellow students and external examiners. In a debate piece in the nationwide newspaper Information (January 29, 2018), several of the Danish universities stated that they were considering introducing specific procedures for cases of sexual harassment in response to the #MeToo debate. The debate pointed out that while it is common practice in the USA and in the other Scandinavian countries to have specific procedures to handle sexual harassment, the Organisation of Danish Universities indicated that the problem in Denmark is not particularly extensive. Thus, sexual harassment was put on the agenda of universities and concrete actions to address the key problems were agreed to be initiated.

The #MeToo movement gained force in the media last year with a public letter initiated by women researchers, putting the issue of harassment of the academic staff on the public agenda for the first time. It was initiated by a group of female researchers from all the Danish universities, followed by a public letter undersigned by 689 researchers, and sent to one of the largest newspapers in the country, Politiken (2020). The debate focused mainly on gender-based discrimination, sexual and other kinds of harassment of the academic staff. Although it had some direct effects as raising the issue for the very first time at a national level, it is very

early to assess the overall impact of the movement on the universities and research organisations.

Last year, two professors and university leaders (a dean and a department head) from Copenhagen University focused on a debate piece in the nationwide newspaper Berlingske (2020) on the Educational Environment Act and suggested making amendments to better address, among others sexual harassment. Employees, such as academic and administrative staff, are protected by the many provisions of the Working Environment Act when they are at work. However, when students enter their place of study at the universities, they are protected only by a few and general provisions of the Education Environment Act. In the debate piece, the professors state that it is a major task for the individual university to formulate guidelines with a view to creating and ensuring a safe and secure environment for students and staff. The task becomes even more complicated by the fact that the Working Environment Act and the Education Environment Act are very different. The former is extensive, involving ten times as many paragraphs as the latter, and that has implications in terms of addressing sexual harassment experienced by students. The professors point out that overall, the university sector has not succeeded to live up to its responsibilities in terms of preventing and dealing with sexual harassment. Among others, they pointed to the fact that the Education Environment Act does not address the prevention and management of sexual harassment in higher education (Berlingske, 2020).

4. PUBLIC OPINION ON GBV

GBV in universities and research organisations has long not been addressed in Denmark, mainly because the public opinion is that there is comprehensive legislation that addresses harassment, sexual harassment, as well as the physical and psychological environment, including harassment in universities and research organisations. However, the delayed #Metoo movement has the two last years raised awareness on harassment, in particular sexual harassment, and ways to address it in almost all sectors, including at the political level.

There are studies, which reveal that, despite the fact that harassment is characterized as a working environment issue by law, a main reason why GBV is not reported is that it is not always perceived as a working environment problem. Many victims experience it as an individual problem because it takes place in locations, such as during a party or in the printing room, where it is not visible, and it is therefore not perceived as an organisational issue. In addition, when employees experience harassment (in particular sexual harassment) and talk about it or report it, many receive comments such as "well, it was just a joke, you can take a joke, can't you?", or "it was a compliment", "you just have to be happy to get attention", or "you are too sensitive". This makes it difficult to take it seriously and tackle it as a working environment problem.

The 2018 survey, mentioned earlier, addressing sexual harassment among students at Danish universities conducted by Universities Denmark and the National Union of Students in Denmark, provided the opportunity to elaborate on the experiences, as well as make recommendations to universities on how the universities can support the victims. Many respondents (more than 400) chose to use this option and answer the open questions. It is interesting to notice that the students asked for more clear guidelines in connection with introductory events and tutorials at the university. The students also asked to be taken seriously when approaching the university

to report sexual harassment and requested more information as to whom to contact at the university in case they experience sexual harassment.

In a study of sexual harassment in academia, the expectation of fun and seriousness and labelling of verbal comments as jokes and humour or as sexual harassment was an ongoing point of negotiation. Thus, some respondents argued that a comment about a person's gender or sexuality is 'just a joke' and thus never to be classified as harassment, while others disagreed, perceiving all comments about gender or sexuality as sexual harassment, reflecting a culture of sexism (Guschke et al 2019). The same study shows that Danes are less likely to perceive certain acts, in particular of verbal character, as sexual harassment. The study concludes that this may point to that the normalization of harassment may be more prominent in the Danish culture compare to other cultures. Internalization of social norms as regards harassment implies the risk to perceive harassment as an individual instead of an organisational issue, which is the responsibility of the university or the research organisation. The study also shows that normalizing certain behaviours of physical, verbal, non-verbal and digital characters in the broader society plays a role in the university context as well. This particular context offers several opportunities for socializing and matchmaking. It is also an international environment with students and staff with different socio-cultural backgrounds and norms (Guschke et al 2019).

Another study among doctors and nurses in Rigshospitalet (University Hospital of Copenhagen) reveals how bullying may develop from an everyday joking practice, in which people relate to each other in the workplace with teasing. This means that the positions of perpetrator and victim constantly change - this excludes the position of a bystander. The study reveals that although doctors and nurses experience the teasing as damaging, at the same time, they feel forced to be part of it, as they fear to be socially excluded - they bully in order to avoid being bullied (Mortensen and Baarts 2018).

5. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON DISCUSSIONS ABOUT GBV

There has been a debate about the impact of Covid-19 as regards GBV in general, but there has not been any particular discussion targeting GBV at universities and research organisations. However, some scholars, mainly gender researchers, have focused on the issue in connection with their research activities.

6. CONCLUSION

Although there are measures and legislation that address GBV in general, GBV in universities and research organisations has for a long time not been subject to special attention at a national level. There is hence limited knowledge about the prevalence of GBV in these specific contexts. The existing knowledge is mainly based on a sexual harassment survey among students initiated by the Universities Denmark and the National Union of Students in Denmark and some other surveys targeting specific sectors or groups of students focusing on mainly the prevalence of sexual harassment. In order to effectively address this complex issue, it is important to first and foremost map the prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution and provision of services as to GBV in universities and research organisations. It is vital to initiate disaggregated data collection and fund GBV research to provide data as a basis for informed policies.

Specific policies at the national level targeting GBV at universities and research organisations are lacking. Current policies are based on limited knowledge of the extent of GBV. While there are some studies on the prevalence of sexual harassment, GBV as a whole is understudied. Lack of data and research on GBV is, therefore, the main problem when it comes to preventing and combating any form of GBV at universities and research organisations. However, the universities have in recent years initiated some actions at an institutional level, based on the results of the 2018 survey on sexual harassment among students and in connection with the #MeToo movement initiated in 2020 by female researchers.

The fact that harassment is perceived as gender equality and working environment issue implies that the handling of harassment and, in particular, sexual harassment has been developed in an area that spans legislation, political and union regulations and criminal law practising. Political decisions on working environment policies in Denmark have prioritized the union track in a way that surpasses the political track in tackling harassment and, in particular sexual harassment. In addition, while there is a general perception that the Danish model for addressing GBV through the union track works, there are union representatives that state that the offended rarely stays in the workplace where the harassment took place. The offender, on the other hand, almost always keeps his/her position. At the same time, there is limited evidence which indicates that organisational learning has taken place based on how these cases have been handled (Borchorst & Agustin, 2017).

In this context - and since there is still progress to be made in this area, a way to move forward is to provide the basis for informed policies, on the one hand, and ensure the necessary measures to introduce and effectively implement concrete policies at the national level targeting GBV at universities and research organisations, on the other. In this connection, specific questions about GBV could be included in the workplace assessments (APV), and more questions and items about GBV could be incorporated in the Education Zoom survey targeting students. Nevertheless, primarily, amendments to the existing legislation are needed on a distinct model for addressing GBV in all higher education to provide the necessary instruments to prevent, protect, prosecute, manage and provide services as to GBV in universities and research organisations.

Another track to pursue moving forward may be to establish a specific independent national observatory on GBV at universities and research organisations and launch networks involving universities, research organisations and other stakeholders.

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